

Study Plan and Results Test Facility Study No. 20335882 Pharmacokinetics of BDT272 Following Oral Administration to Male Wistar Han Rats	
Test Facility: Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch Hambakenwetering 7 5231 DD, 's-Hertogenbosch The Netherlands	Sponsor: Biodol Therapeutics CAP Alpha 9 Avenue De l'Europe 34830 Clapiers France
Study Director: Coordinating Biotechnician: Handling of blood samples: Necropsy: Individual Scientist Bioanalysis: Pharmacokinetic Evaluation:	Moniek van 't Root Address as cited for Test Facility Moniek.vantroot@crl.com Luuk Hooijmans Paula Polman Her/necropsy Harold Darwinkel Mirelle Engels
Sponsor Representative:	Pierre Sokoloff Tel: +33 7 70 41 63 68 E-mail: pierre.sokoff@biodol.eu
Test Facility Study No:	20335882
Compliance:	Not claiming GLP compliance
Animal Arrival Date: Experimental Starting Date Projected Dosing Date: Experimental Completion Date: Proposed Sample Shipment Date:	10 Nov 2021 17 Nov 2021 17 Nov 2021 18 Nov 2021 18 Nov 2021 The Bioanalytical study will be performed at the Groningen location, all other supporting activities will be performed at the 's-Hertogenbosch location.
Study Objective:	To determine the intrinsic pharmacokinetics of the test compounds to enable the selection of molecules to progress into in vivo pharmacology models.
Test System:	Rat: Crl:WI(Han), Outbred, SPF-Quality, Charles River Deutschland, Sulzfeld, Germany. The 24 male animals will be 8 to 10 weeks old with a body weight ranging between 200 to 300 gram at initiation of dosing.
Guidelines and Animal Welfare	The Wistar Han rat was chosen as the animal model for this study as it is an accepted rodent species for preclinical toxicity testing by regulatory agencies. This study has been designed such that it does not require an unnecessary number of animals to accomplish its objectives. There are no applicable guidelines for the conduct of this screening study. This study plan was reviewed and agreed by the Animal Welfare Body of Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V. within the framework of Appendix 1 of project license AVD2360020173904 approved by the Central Authority for Scientific Procedures on Animals (CCD) as required by the Dutch Act on Animal Experimentation (December 2014).

Animal Housing and Husbandry:	<p>Animals will be socially housed (up to 3 animals of the same group) in polycarbonate cages (Makrolon type IV, height 18 cm) containing appropriate bedding (Lignocel S 8-15, JRS - J.Rettenmaier & Söhne GmbH + CO. KG, Rosenberg, Germany) equipped with water bottles, unless contraindicated by study procedures (such as pharmacokinetic blood sampling) or clinical signs.</p> <p>These housing conditions will be maintained unless deemed inappropriate by the Study Director and/or Clinical Veterinarian. The room(s) in which the animals will be kept will be documented in the study records. Veterinary care will be available.</p> <p>Pelleted rodent diet (SM R/M-Z from SSNIFF® Spezialdiäten GmbH, Soest, Germany) will be provided ad libitum throughout the study, except during designated procedures.</p>					
Test Item(s):	BDT272 (213138/A)					
Dose Vehicle(s):	7% Tween80 in 0.9% NaCl					
Dose Formulation Preparation:	<p>The dose formulation will be prepared on the day of dose administration.</p> <p>The test item will be dissolved in the vehicle to meet dose level requirements. The formulations will be stirred, vortexed and/or sonicated to obtain a homogeneous formulation.</p> <p>Any residual volumes will be discarded unless otherwise requested by the Study Director.</p>					
Study Design:						
Group	Test Item Name	Route of administration	Dose level mg/kg	Dose volume mL/kg	Number of Animals	Animal Numbers
					Males	Males
1	BDT272	po by oral gavage	5	10	6	1-6
2	BDT272	iv into tail vein	1	5	6	7-12
<p>¹ Test item will be used intended to be used as the treatment of pain disorders;</p> <p>² The doses are relatively low and chosen to minimise the prospect achieving any potential on target / off target toxicity and of achieving non-linear PK as a consequence of saturation of in vivo drug metabolism pathways.</p>						
Treatment:	<p>Groups 1: Oral gavage using plastic feeding tube.</p> <p>Groups 2: The test item will be administered to the appropriate animals via a single intravenous (bolus) injection to the tail vein. The animals will be temporarily restrained for dose administration and will not be sedated.</p>					
Observations:	<p>BW prior to dosing.</p> <p>Clinical signs during dosing and sample collection period.</p> <p>Animals showing pain, distress or discomfort which is considered not transient in nature or is likely to become more severe, will be sacrificed for humane reasons based on OECD guidance document on humane endpoints (ENV/JM/MONO/ 2000/7). The circumstances of any death will be recorded in detail.</p> <p>(Test Facility Study No. for Toxdata (in-life phase) and tissue weights: 523400).</p>					

		PK Sample Collection Schedule							
Group No.	Sample Collection Time Points (Time Postdose)								
	0.5h	1h	2h	3h	4h	6h	8h	24h	
Subject numbers									
1	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	
2	7-9	7-9	7-9	7-9	7-9	7-9	7-9	7-9	

Group Number	Terminal CSF Collection (Post dose)
1	Animal Nos. 4-6: 2 hours
2	Animal Nos. 10-12: 2 hours
Volume/Timepoint	Minimally 30 μ L

Bioanalytical Sample Collection: From animals in Groups 1 and 2 blood will be collected according to the PK sample collection table (outlined above). Approximately 0.2 mL blood samples will be taken from the jugular vein and collected into tubes containing K₂ EDTA as anti-coagulant and stored on ice.

Sample Processing and Storage: Whole blood will be processed to plasma by centrifugation (3000g for 10 minutes at 2-8°C) within 1 hour of collection. Plasma samples will be transferred into labeled polypropylene Micronic tubes and stored in an ultra-low freezer set to maintain -80°C until shipment.

CSF Sample Collection: The volume of the collected CSF will be recorded. If blood contamination occurs when collecting CSF, this will be recorded. CSF will be stored on wet ice after collection. CSF will be stored within 30 minutes after collection in labeled polypropylene Micronic tubes in an ultra-low freezer set to maintain -80°C until shipment on dry ice.

Bioanalysis: Plasma samples and CSF samples will be analyzed for the concentration of BDT272 using a non-qualified analytical procedure with reference Key 2371. Statistical analyses including regression analysis and descriptive statistics including arithmetic means and standard deviations, accuracy and precision will be performed. General data concerning chemicals, reagents, preparation of stock solutions, calibration standards, and quality control samples (QCs) as well as the analytical conditions will be stored in the study file. Any residual/retained bioanalytical samples will be discarded upon authorization by the Study Director.

Pharmacokinetic Evaluation: Pharmacokinetic parameters will be calculated from the individual curves, using the Phoenix WinNonlin 6.4 program. Non-compartmental analysis with the oral and intravenous route of administration will be applied. All parameters will be generated from BDT272 and BDT4046 individual concentrations in plasma. Individual values below the LLOQ will be taken as zero in calculating the descriptive statistics. Parameters to be calculated are (if data allow): C_{max} and t_{max}, t_{last}, AUC_{last}, AUC_∞, λ_z, t_{1/2} and F.

Terminal Procedure After the last blood sampling, the animals will be deeply anaesthetized using oxygen/carbon dioxide. No necropsy will be performed and no tissues will be collected.

Shipping:	<p>Plasma samples and CSF samples will be shipped on dry-ice to:</p> <p>Charles River Laboratories Groningen B.V. De Mudden 16 9747 AW Groningen The Netherlands</p> <p>The shipping contact at Charles River Groningen is Harold Darwinkel (Harold.darwinkel@crl.com).</p>
Reporting:	<p>QC-checked Bioanalytical Results (Excel sheet): 03 Dec 2021 QC-checked Pharmacokinetic Evaluation Results (Excel sheet): 17 Dec 2021 In-life Results (Excel sheet): 28 Dec 2021</p>
Archiving:	Two years following issuance of the tabulated data.
Study Plan Approved By: Moniek van 't Root, MSc Study Director, Charles River	All electronic signatures appear at the end of the document upon finalization.
Study Plan Approved By: Pierre Sokoloff Sponsor Representative, Biodol Therapeutics	<p>The Study Plan was approved by the Sponsor by e-mail on the date designated below. The correspondence giving approval will be archived, as appropriate with other Sponsor communications.</p> <p><u>09 Nov 2021</u> Date of Sponsor Approval</p>

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SIGNATURE(S) FOR DOCUMENT: 20335882 - Study Plan

Study Director
Approval: I approve this document.

Name: **van 't Root, Moniek**

van 't Root, Moniek

11-Nov-2021 11:19:12 (UTC+00:00)

Electronically Signed in

Timestamp

RESULTS

CRL Project 20335882

Test Item:

Test Item Identification	Test Item Number
BDT272	213138/A

Test System:

Rat: CrI:WI(HAN), Outbred, SPF-Quality, Charles River Deutschland, Sulzfeld, Germany.

Study Design:

Group	Test Item Name	Route of administration	Dose level (mg/kg)	Dose volume (mL/kg)	Number of Animals	Animal Numbers
					Males	Males
1	BDT272	po by oral gavage	5	10	6	1-6
2	BDT272	iv into tail vein	1	5	6	7-12

PK Sample Collection Schedule:

Group No.	PK Sample Collection Schedule (Time Postdose)					
	0.083h	0.25h	0.5h	1h	2h	3h
	Subject numbers					
1	n/s	n/s	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3
2	7-9	7-9	7-9	7-9	7-9	n/s
	PK Sample Collection Schedule (Time Postdose)					
	4h	6h	8h	24h		
	Subject numbers					
1	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3		
2	7-9	n/s	7-9	7-9		

n/s: no sample scheduled

Group Number	Terminal CSF Collection (Post dose)
1	Animal Nos. 4-6: 2 hours
2	Animal Nos. 10-12: 2 hours
Volume/Timepoint	Minimally 30 µL

Vehicle:

7% Tween80 in 0.9% NaCl

Formulation:

Clinical Observations:

No clinical signs were noted.
See attached PDF scan.

Body weight and dose volume:

See attached PDF scan.

Sample Collection Details

All samples were collected on the planned sampling time, with the exception of:

Animal No.	Nominal Sampling Time (h)	Actual Sampling Time (h)
7	1	1.02
2	2	2.02
3	2	2.02
1	8	8.02

The following plasma samples were hemolytic:

- Animal No. 9: 0.25 hour
- Animal No. 1: 2 hours
- Animal No. 7: 2 hours
- Animal No. 7: 4 hours
- Animal No. 1: 6 hours
- Animal No. 1: 8 hours
- Animal No. 1: 24 hours

- Animal No. 1: 2 hours

All CSF samples were collected on the planned sampling time, with the exception of:

Animal No.	Nominal Sampling Time (h)	Actual Sampling Time (h)
10	2	2.02

The following CSF samples were contaminated with blood:

- Animal No.
12

Matrix : plasma

				Concentration (ng/mL)
Group	Animal no	Time point (hr)	Matrix	BDT272
1	1	0.5	Plasma	118.800
1	2	0.5	Plasma	120.600
1	3	0.5	Plasma	92.970
1	1	1	Plasma	110.300
1	2	1	Plasma	111.000
1	3	1	Plasma	110.200
1	1	2	Plasma	144.700
1	2	2	Plasma	104.900
1	3	2	Plasma	131.800
			Mean ± S.D. at 2 h	127.1 ± 20.3
1	1	3	Plasma	85.900
1	2	3	Plasma	127.300
1	3	3	Plasma	112.500
1	1	4	Plasma	98.080
1	2	4	Plasma	128.800
1	3	4	Plasma	119.700
1	1	6	Plasma	87.440
1	2	6	Plasma	110.300
1	3	6	Plasma	134.500
1	1	8	Plasma	93.010
1	2	8	Plasma	113.700
1	3	8	Plasma	94.660
1	1	24	Plasma	16.890
1	2	24	Plasma	9.320
1	3	24	Plasma	20.420
2	7	0.083	Plasma	150.400
2	8	0.083	Plasma	153.300
2	9	0.083	Plasma	150.200
2	7	0.25	Plasma	109.600
2	8	0.25	Plasma	126.900
2	9	0.25	Plasma	117.600
2	7	0.5	Plasma	93.880
2	8	0.5	Plasma	79.810
2	9	0.5	Plasma	72.900
2	7	1	Plasma	66.050
2	8	1	Plasma	65.410
2	9	1	Plasma	58.710
2	7	2	Plasma	45.180
2	8	2	Plasma	32.920
2	9	2	Plasma	31.360

2	7	4	Plasma	20.700
2	8	4	Plasma	22.760
2	9	4	Plasma	23.660
2	7	8	Plasma	11.260
2	8	8	Plasma	10.570
2	9	8	Plasma	9.074
2	7	24	Plasma	< LLOQ
2	8	24	Plasma	< LLOQ
2	9	24	Plasma	< LLOQ
Matrix : Cerebrospinal fluid				
				Concentration (ng/mL)
Group	Aninal no	Time point (hr)	Matrix	BDT272
1	4	2	CSF	21.0
1	5	2	CSF	19.9
1	6	2	CSF	6.35
2	10	2	CSF	4.50
2	11	2	CSF	3.25
2	12	2	CSF	3.94
			Mean	9.8
			S.D.	3.4

LLOQ of BDT272 in plasma: 2 ng/mL

LLOQ of BDT272 in CSF: 1 ng/mL

20335882 PK Table

Analyte		BDT272					
Route		PO					
Dose Level		5					
Animal		1	2	3	Mean	SD	CV%
t _{last}	h	24	24	24	24	n/a	n/a
t _{max}	h	2	4	6	2-6\$	n/a	n/a
C _{max}	ng/mL	145	129	135	136	8.06	6
C _{max} /Dose	kg·ng/mL/mg	28.9	25.8	26.9	27.2	1.61	6
AUC _{last}	h·ng/mL	1670	1890	1840	1800	116	6
AUC _{last} /Dose	h·kg·ng/mL/mg	333	377	367	359	23.1	6
AUC _∞	h·ng/mL	1840	1950	n/c	1900	ID	ID
AUC _∞ /Dose	h·kg·ng/mL/mg	368	390	n/c	379	ID	ID
%extrapolated	%	9	3	n/c	n/a	n/a	n/a
λ _z	1/h	0.0972	0.145	n/c	0.121	ID	ID
t _{1/2}	h	7.13	4.79	n/c	5.96	ID	ID
No. of points		3	3	n/c	n/a	n/a	n/a
r ²		0.9823	0.9875	n/c	n/a	n/a	n/a
F	%	n/a	n/a	n/a	120	n/a	n/a
Route		IV					
Dose Level		1					
Animal		7	8	9	Mean	SD	CV%
t _{last}	h	8	8	8	8	n/a	n/a
C ₀	ng/mL	176	168	170	171	4.09	2
AUC _{last}	h·ng/mL	286	270	258	271	14.1	5
AUC _∞	h·ng/mL	325	326	301	317	14.2	4
%extrapolated	%	12	17	14	n/a	n/a	n/a
λ _z	1/h	0.292	0.190	0.211	0.231	0.0536	23
t _{1/2}	h	2.38	3.65	3.28	3.10	0.656	21
No. of points		6	3	3	n/a	n/a	n/a
r ²		0.9343	0.9999	0.9868	n/a	n/a	n/a
V _z	mL/kg	10600	16200	15700	14200	3110	22
Cl	mL/h/kg	3080	3070	3320	3160	145	5
V _{ss}	mL/kg	10200	12700	12500	11800	1380	12

\$: range; n/a: not applicable; n/c: could not be calculated; NR: not reported; ID: insufficient data.

PK i.v., p.o. (rat)

1.1 CLINICAL SIGNS MALES

SIGN (MAX. GRADE) (LOCATION)	TREATMENT	
	WEEK:1.	DAY: 12
GROUP 1 (GROUP 1)		
ANIMAL 1	No clinical signs noted	ANIMAL 2 No clinical signs noted
ANIMAL 3	No clinical signs noted	ANIMAL 4 No clinical signs noted
ANIMAL 5	No clinical signs noted	ANIMAL 6
No clinical signs noted		
GROUP 2 (GROUP 2)		
ANIMAL 7	No clinical signs noted	ANIMAL 8 No clinical signs noted
ANIMAL 9	No clinical signs noted	ANIMAL 10 No clinical signs noted
ANIMAL 11	No clinical signs noted	ANIMAL 12
No clinical signs noted		

G: Highest daily grades
.: Observation performed, sign not present

26Nov21 09h02

1.2 BODY WEIGHTS (GRAM) MALES

DAYS 1
WEEKS 1
ANIMAL

GROUP 1 (GROUP 1)

1	244
2	245
3	226
4	237
5	225
6	246

GROUP 2 (GROUP 2)

7	241
8	233

9	238
10	240
11	234
12	227

26Nov21 09h02

APPLIKATIONSMENGEN VOM 17-NOV-21 (PO)

Tier	Sex	Gr.	Applikationsmenge [ML]	Körpergewicht [g]	Phase/Tag	Dosis [MG/KG]	Volumen/KG [ML]
1	M	1	2.4	244	1 / 1	5.0	10
2	M	1	2.5	245	1 / 1	5.0	10
3	M	1	2.3	226	1 / 1	5.0	10
4	M	1	2.4	237	1 / 1	5.0	10
5	M	1	2.3	225	1 / 1	5.0	10
6	M	1	2.5	246	1 / 1	5.0	10
7	M	2	1.2	241	1 / 1	1.0	5
8	M	2	1.2	233	1 / 1	1.0	5
9	M	2	1.2	238	1 / 1	1.0	5
10	M	2	1.2	240	1 / 1	1.0	5
11	M	2	1.2	234	1 / 1	1.0	5
12	M	2	1.1	227	1 / 1	1.0	5
13	M	3	2.4	242	1 / 1	5.0	10
14	M	3	2.3	231	1 / 1	5.0	10
15	M	3	2.3	233	1 / 1	5.0	10
16	M	3	2.3	227	1 / 1	5.0	10
17	M	3	2.5	254	1 / 1	5.0	10
18	M	3	2.3	233	1 / 1	5.0	10
19	M	4	1.2	239	1 / 1	1.0	5
20	M	4	1.2	244	1 / 1	1.0	5
21	M	4	1.2	235	1 / 1	1.0	5
22	M	4	1.2	243	1 / 1	1.0	5
23	M	4	1.2	231	1 / 1	1.0	5
24	M	4	1.1	219	1 / 1	1.0	5

Gedoseerd door:

JwI 17 nov 2021

APPLIKATIONSMENGEN VOM 17-NOV-21 (PO)

Tier	Sex	Gr.	Applikationsmenge [ML]	Körpergewicht [g]	Phase/Tag	Dosis [MG/KG]	Volumen/KG [ML]
1	M	1	2.4	244	1 / 1	5.0	10
2	M	1	2.5	245	1 / 1	5.0	10
3	M	1	2.3	226	1 / 1	5.0	10
4	M	1	2.4	237	1 / 1	5.0	10
5	M	1	2.3	225	1 / 1	5.0	10
6	M	1	2.5	246	1 / 1	5.0	10
7	M	2	1.2	241	1 / 1	1.0	5
8	M	2	1.2	233	1 / 1	1.0	5
9	M	2	1.2	238	1 / 1	1.0	5
10	M	2	1.2	240	1 / 1	1.0	5
11	M	2	1.2	234	1 / 1	1.0	5
12	M	2	1.1	227	1 / 1	1.0	5
13	M	3	2.4	242	1 / 1	5.0	10
14	M	3	2.3	231	1 / 1	5.0	10
15	M	3	2.3	233	1 / 1	5.0	10
16	M	3	2.3	227	1 / 1	5.0	10
17	M	3	2.5	254	1 / 1	5.0	10
18	M	3	2.3	233	1 / 1	5.0	10
19	M	4	1.2	239	1 / 1	1.0	5
20	M	4	1.2	244	1 / 1	1.0	5
21	M	4	1.2	235	1 / 1	1.0	5
22	M	4	1.2	243	1 / 1	1.0	5
23	M	4	1.2	231	1 / 1	1.0	5
24	M	4	1.1	219	1 / 1	1.0	5

Gedoseerd door: *Paul Franzen*